

Spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI) using 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(4'-tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

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Abstract : A new, simple, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method is developed for the trace determination of tungsten. A light yellow (1 : 2) complex of tungsten(VI) is formed with 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(4'-tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMTB) in perchloric acid medium. The coloured species is extracted into chloroform and absorbance is measured at 396-402 nm. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0-9.5 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$, with a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $1.43 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0013 \mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 398 nm. The method is free from the interference of a large number of elements and has been applied for the determination of tungsten in a variety of samples with satisfactory accuracy.

Keywords : W^{VI} , spectrophotometric, extraction, determination.

Introduction

Several spectrophotometric methods have been reported for the determination of tungsten. Most of them are unsatisfactory for different reasons. In these methods the interference of various metals, the stability of the complex, low sensitivity¹⁻³, non-selectivity, complexity in the procedures and time consumption have been the main problems. Other reported methods using several organic reagents²⁻⁶ for this purpose also suffer from one or more of these drawbacks. This has appreciated to search for new better methods which are simpler, more sensitive, selective and rapid. Accordingly, 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(4'-tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMTB) has been used as a complexing agent to meet the above requirements.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : The absorbance of W^{VI} -HMTB complex in chloroform was greatly influenced by the nature of acids. From 1 M acidity fixed in each case, the absorbance was found to decrease in the order : HClO_4 (0.780) > H_2SO_4 (0.720) > HCl (0.70) > HNO_3 (0.68) > CH_3COOH (0.240) > H_3PO_4 (0.18). The complex gave very low absorbance (0.02) in neutral as well as in alkaline me-

dium. Therefore, HClO_4 medium was preferred for further studies.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : Various organic solvents namely chloroform, benzene, dichloromethane, 1,2-dichloroethane, toluene, ethyl acetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl alcohol, isoamyl acetate, carbontetrachloride and cyclohexane extracted the W^{VI} -HMTB complex in the decreasing order of absorbance. As chloroform gave maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was chosen as the most suitable extractant. A single equilibrium of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform under conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of W^{VI} -HMTB complex. The complete absence of tungsten in the raffinate was tested by more sensitive method³.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorption spectra of the W^{VI} -HMTB complex and the reagent blank are shown in Fig. 1. W^{VI} -HMTB complex in 1 M HClO_4 has an absorption maximum at 398 nm. In chloroform, the absorbance remains same for more than 24 h at this wavelength.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of W^{VI} -HMTB complex in chloroform : Curve A - Complex against reagent blank; Curve B - Reagent blank against pure chloroform; Concentration of W^{VI} - 0.271×10^{-4} ; Concentration of HMTB - 0.1% (w/v) in ethanol.

Effect of concentration of $HClO_4$, HMTB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The optimum values of above parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were 0.8–6.0 ml $HClO_4$, 0.6–1.2 ml of 0.1% HMTB (in ethanol) and 5–100 s equilibration time for $\leq 95 \mu g W^{VI}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of the reagent and $HClO_4$ should be kept same throughout as per proposed procedure as on changing this order, low absorbance is observed. Beer's law was valid in the concentration range of 0–9.5 $\mu g W^{VI} ml^{-1}$. However the optimum range for the determination of tungsten, as evaluated from Ringbom plot⁸, was calculated to be 1.12–7.24 $\mu g W^{VI} ml^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sen-

sitivity of the complex at 398 nm were $1.43 \times 10^5 dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$ and $0.0013 \mu g W cm^{-2}$, respectively. The ratio of W^{VI} and HMTB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburg and Cooper⁹ for a two-phase system.

This was further confirmed by mole ratio and equilibrium shift methods. On the basis of the spectrophotometric methods the most probable structure of the W^{VI} -HMTB complex is as given below :

W^{VI} -HMTB complex

Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in parentheses), nitrate, sulfate, chloride, bromide, iodide, ascorbic acid, sulphosalicylic acid (100 each), thiourea (90), nitrite (80), sulphite (70), acetate (50), dithionite (35), phosphate (20), carbonate (10), EDTA (8), fluoride (1), citrate (0.1), glycerol (1 ml), H_2O_2 (30% w/v) (0.1 ml) were without effect. However oxalate and tartarate even in traces interfered seriously. Among the cations Sb^{III} , As^{III} , Cd^{II} , Ag^I ,

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of W-complex

$HClO_4$ (M) ^a	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08–0.6	0.64	0.66
Absorbance	0.240	0.44	0.680	0.780	0.760	0.720
0.1% HMTB (ml) ^b	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6–1.2	1.4	1.6
Absorbance	0.420	0.51	0.620	0.780	0.700	0.600
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	2	5	8–100		
Absorbance	0.080	0.62	0.740	0.780		

^a W^{VI} = 50 μg , $HClO_4$ = variable, 0.1% HMTB = 1 ml, equilibration time = 15 s, solvent = chloroform, aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml, number of extractions = 1.

^b $HClO_4$ = 0.1 M, other conditions being same as in (a) except for the variation in HMTB concentration also HMTB = 3-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(4'-tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran.

^c0.1% (w/v) HMTB in ethanol = 1 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	(i) Solvent (ii) (λ_{\max} , nm)	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Interfering metal ions
1.	W ^{VI} , 10 M HCl, 25% KSCN, 30% SnCl ₂ , 0.5% quinaldic acid, heat to 80 °C, colour development time 10 min ^d	Isoamyl acetate (405)	0.012 (1.51×10^4)	Pd ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Re ^{VII} , V ^V , Pt ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI}
2.	W ^{VI} , 0.12–0.26 M HClO ₄ , 0.9–2.5 ml of 0.002 M HL in ethanol ^b	Dichloromethane (410)	0.0039 (4.69×10^4)	Mo ^{VI} , Zr ^{VI} , Nb, Th, Ce and Rh
3.	W ^{VI} , 0.2 M HClO ₄ , 0.5–1.3 ml of 0.1% 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in acetone ^c	Dichloromethane (407)	0.0049 (3.78×10^4)	–
4.	W ^{VI} , 1 M HCl, 0.6–1.6 ml of 0.05% HPB in acetone ^d	Dichloromethane (391)	0.00434 (4.29×10^4)	V ^V , Mo ^{VI}
5.	Proposed method	Chloroform (398)	0.0013 (1.43×10^5)	35 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef. = 2, ^bRef. = 11, ^cRef. = 10, ^dRef. = 12.

Mn^{II}, Se^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^I, Mg^{II}, Al^{III}, Bi^{III} (100 each); Be^{II}, Cu^{II}, U^{VI} (5 each); Ru^{III}, Os^{VIII} (3 each); Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV} (2 each); Rh^{III}, Ta^V, Nb^V, Pd^{II} (1 each); Pt^{II} (0.5), Re^{VII} (0.4), Au^{III} (0.1), Ti^{IV} (0.08) and Fe^{III} (0.05) caused < 1% error in absorbance. V^V and Mo^{VI} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Application : The wide applicability of the method was tested by carrying out the analysis of various synthetic samples with satisfactory results. The proposed spectrophotometric method is highly selective, sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of analytically important metal ions. The results obtained were highly reproducible with a standard deviation of ± 0.0026 absorbance units.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 140-02 (UV-Visible) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells were used for absorbance measurements and spectral studies. A standard stock solution (100 ml) of tungsten(vi) containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amounts (0.179 g) of sodium tungstate (A.R., CDH) in deionized water. Lower concentrations at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level were prepared by suitable dilution therefrom. Solutions of other ions were prepared at mg ml⁻¹ level by

dissolving their sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acids. They were suitably diluted to obtain lower concentrations of the metal ions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level. Perchloric acid (1 M) was prepared by diluting the acid with deionized water. 3-Hydroxy-6-methyl-2-(4'-tolyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMTB) (m.p. 180 °C) needed for the present study was prepared by the procedure reported in the literature for the preparation of flavonols¹³ and dissolved in pure ethanol to get 0.1% (w/v) solution. Chloroform (Ranbaxy) was used as such. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing a known volume of tungsten(vi) solution with solutions of other metal ions in suitable proportions.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing ≤ 95 μg tungsten(vi) and other ions taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel 1 M HClO₄ (1 ml), 0.1% (w/v) HMTB in ethanol (1 ml) were added along with sufficient deionized water to make the volume to 10 ml. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of chloroform for 15 s. The light yellow organic phase was separated. The absorbance of the complex in the extract was measured at 398 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the amount of tungsten was determined from the standard curve prepared in an analogous manner. Modifications for the samples containing V^V and Mo^{VI} : for 0.1 mg of V^V and Mo^{VI}; 0.1 ml of 6% (w/v) H₂O₂ was added as masking agent, prior to the addition of HMTB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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